

**HISTORY AND PROSPECTS OF MULTILATERAL DIPLOMACY OF
UZBEKISTAN.**

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Abstract: This article covers the history of the diplomacy of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its future prospects, and the current activities in the fields of culture, education, and science in our country are analyzed in detail.

Keywords: diplomacy, international cultural relations, United Nations General Assembly, Central Asia at the crossroads of world civilizations, religious freedom, Internatoinal Friendship Day

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INTRODUCTION

After gaining independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan began practical efforts to develop foreign political directions in various fields. Uzbekistan has set itself the main task of conducting not only a consistent internal policy, but also an active foreign policy, and is systematically working towards this goal. It is known from history that the first states that existed in the territory of Uzbekistan: the Turkish khanate, the Arab caliphate, the Timurids and the three khanates, diplomacy was the main area of attention of the state, because strengthening independence, security, stability and development of the country largely depends on the active foreign policy conducted with foreign countries. Our country, which is located on the Great Silk Road, has formed economic, political and cultural relations with foreign countries for centuries and maintained mutual diplomatic relations. This process developed especially during the time of the great statesman, Sahibgiron Amir Temur. Amir Temur, in addition to being the founder of one of the most powerful states of his time, a patron of science and culture, had a decisive influence on the historical changes that took place in Europe and Asia during his time. He was also a skilled diplomat who made an incomparable contribution to the development of world civilization. In his correspondence with the rulers of foreign countries, in his diplomatic letters, the etiquette characteristic of eastern diplomacy is clearly noticeable, the coldness between the countries and his desire to solve problems peacefully are evidences of the uniqueness of Amir Temur's foreign policy. That is why the diplomacy of the Timurid period is one of the brightest pages of international relations in the past. Six centuries ago, Amir Temur deeply understood that the country's prospects cannot be achieved without establishing

foreign relations with foreign countries. Correspondence and diplomatic relations with the rulers of different countries such as England, France, Ottoman Turks, Spain, China, and India are a clear confirmation of this. Despite the fact that our country has produced many skilled diplomats and ambassadors like Amir Temur, their activities have not been studied in depth. The head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, said about this in his speech dedicated to the activities of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan and embassies abroad on January 11, 2018. There is a lot of information about the development of diplomats and ambassadors, but their life and activities, unfortunately, have not been studied in depth and comprehensively so far. "If the Ministry of Foreign Affairs pays attention to this and publishes a separate book about the historical roots of this issue and the processes of formation of Uzbek diplomacy during the period of independence, it would be an important guide for the employees of this field, first of all, for young diplomats," he said. In the 19th century, the countries located on the territory of Uzbekistan, after being colonized by the Russian Empire, were deprived of the right to conduct an independent foreign policy, lost their sovereignty, and were forced to serve only the interests of the center had fallen. But after the centuries-old dreams of our people came true and we achieved independence, the first steps of the diplomacy of sovereign Uzbekistan were taken.

In particular, in order to effectively establish the foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, to create favorable external conditions for the political and socio-economic development of the Republic, to represent and protect the interests of citizens and the state of the Republic of Uzbekistan in international relations and in foreign countries. On May 25, 1992, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers "On issues of organizing the activities of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted. The foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On improving the activities of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan" adopted in March 1994 and "On the main principles of the foreign policy activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan" in 1996 was formed based on decisions. Due to this, during the years of independence, our country established official relations with more than 133 countries, currently 45 embassies of foreign countries, 9 consulates, and 11 representative offices of international organizations are operating in Tashkent. The main principles, principles, strategic priorities, goals and objectives of the Foreign Policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan are reflected in the "Concept of Foreign Political Activity" adopted in September 2012. This concept is a comprehensive system of views that defines the priorities that advance the national interests of Uzbekistan.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The Republic of Uzbekistan pursued an active and peaceful foreign policy for the development of multilateral cooperation relations. For example, on March 2, 1992, the Republic of Uzbekistan became an equal member of the United Nations and began to put forward various proposals on behalf of the country at international forums. In particular, the proposals made to strengthen peace and stability in the whole world, establish peace in Afghanistan, support the socio-economic development of nations, and prevent the spread of nuclear weapons were enthusiastically supported by the UN, which strives to unite the world community. Uzbekistan has established wide-scale cooperative relations with a number of specialized institutions of the UN, including the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the World Bank, the UN Economic Commission for Europe (EEC), the World Trade Organization (WTO). Also, the Republic of Uzbekistan became a member of specialized institutions within the UN: the International Children's Fund (UNICEF), the World Health Organization, the International Olympic Committee, the International Labor Organization and other organizations. Due to some shortcomings encountered in the system during cooperation with international organizations, while gaining high ratings in foreign policy, foreign relations in our country weakened significantly for a while. Especially, this situation began to be felt from the mid-2000s. Many problems have appeared in the system as a result of the weakening of cooperation in various fields with foreign countries, most importantly, with countries bordering our country. However, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, who was elected as the president in the last quarter of 2016, deeply understood this situation and paid special attention to the fact that it is a priority task to critically review and strengthen the foreign policy system as well as various fields. A number of practical works have been carried out in this regard. In particular, in January 2018, for the first time in the history of our country, the head of our country held an open online dialogue with ambassadors of Uzbekistan in foreign countries. In addition, in 2017, a conference was held in Samarkand with the participation of more than 500 delegates on the theme "Central Asia: a common history and a common future, cooperation for progress and sustainable development".

The head of our state defined the strengthening and development of friendly, close neighborly and mutually beneficial relations with Central Asian countries as the main foreign policy direction. The unity of our history, religion, culture, and language, and the intertwining of our veins, in the current dangerous times, have begun to demand more than ever the need to bring the peoples of these countries closer together. At the initiative of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, a new era began in Uzbekistan's relations with neighboring countries in 2017. In the same year, state visits were made to Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan. As a result of strengthening the open and reliable political dialogue between the heads of state, a

solution was found to many complex problems that existed in the neighborhood relations in the region until 2016. The modern foreign policy of Uzbekistan is being built taking into account the rapidly changing international and political realities of the 21st century, which require an active, proactive and pragmatic foreign policy course and a timely response to emerging threats. These indicate that Uzbekistan has strong relations with the world community and is deepening mutually beneficial cooperation. 40 "roadmaps" have been developed and are being implemented together with our foreign partners in order to fully implement the documents and agreements adopted within the framework of international cooperation. Under the conditions of complex geopolitical processes in the world, the coronavirus pandemic and the global economic crisis, Uzbekistan conducts an open and pragmatic active foreign policy. As a result of our determined efforts in the international arena, the prestige and reputation of our country is increasing more and more. Our country is gaining its place among the countries of the world. In particular, our country was elected a member of the UN Human Rights Council for the first time in its history. The recent removal of Uzbekistan from the list of "countries under special surveillance" in the field of religious freedom by the US State Department is also a recognition of our large-scale democratic reforms. The global and regional initiatives put forward by Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the highest podium of the United Nations General Assembly on September 19, 2017 were accepted and supported by the world community with great interest. In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis, held on December 29, 2020, it was mentioned that the following tasks will be given priority in the implementation of the foreign policy of our country in 2021:

Particular attention is paid to further strengthening our relations with the Central Asian countries, which are among the priorities of our foreign policy, in the spirit of centuries-old friendship and good neighborliness, strategic partnership and mutual trust. The complex pandemic conditions have once again clearly demonstrated how dependent and necessary we are. In order to deeply study and further develop these positive processes, the International Institute of Central Asia was established in Tashkent in 2020. In 2021, a high-level international conference on the relations of our region with South Asia was held in Tashkent. Among these, the international conference "Central Asia at the Crossroads of World Civilizations" was held in Khiva in cooperation with UNESCO. Issues of developing close cooperation with the United Nations Organization and other influential international and regional organizations are always in the center of our attention. In 2020, our country chaired the Commonwealth of Independent States for the first time, and despite the pandemic, all planned more than 60 international events were

successfully held, and about 70 important documents were adopted. On September 15-16, 2022, he chaired the Shanghai Cooperation Organization of Uzbekistan. To consistently strengthen our progress in ensuring human rights, freedom of speech and religious belief in cooperation with relevant international organizations, and next year, under the auspices of the United Nations, the global forum "Education on Human Rights", youth rights It is intended to hold a dedicated World Youth Conference, regional conferences on religious freedom issues. He emphasized that our efforts aimed at strengthening the environment of inter-ethnic harmony and tolerance in the society should be brought to a qualitatively new level. It is known that by the resolution of the General Assembly of the United Nations, July 30 is widely celebrated as International Friendship Day. Therefore, the head of our state suggested that this date be designated as "People's Friendship Day" in Uzbekistan. It was mentioned that the deteriorating environmental situation in our region and in the whole world is of serious concern to us, and that together with the neighboring countries and the world community, we must continue efforts aimed at mitigating the effects of the environmental tragedies caused by the Aral Sea disaster.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, Uzbekistan has been establishing mutually beneficial relations with many countries on earth in various fields.

is consistently and determinedly moving towards strengthening international security and stability, developing all forms of cooperation. In this age of global competition, conflict, conflict of interests, and geopolitical conflicts, we cannot achieve our goals without a strong foreign policy.

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